

INDEX NUMBER.....

HOLY FNMTC-BEREKUM
END OF SEMESTER EXAMINATION- MAY 2019
RGN 20: MANAGEMENT AND ADMINISTRATION IN NURSING: RMD 321
TIME ALLOWED: 2HOURS
ESSAY

INSTRUCTIONS:

- Answer all questions
- Each question must be answered in a separate booklet
- Each question carries 20marks
- Read the question carefully and provide only relevant answers
- Note that any number of points provided beyond the NUMBER SPECIFIED for each question will not attract any mark.

QUESTION ONE

- a. Explain briefly any **five (5)** dimensions of quality. - 10 Marks
- b. List the **five (5)** main Quality Assurance Principles - 5 Marks
- c. Mention any **five (5)** differences between a leader and a manager - 5 Marks

QUESTION TWO

- a. Mention any **three (3)** advantages and **three (3)** disadvantages of a pyramidal organisational structure. - 6 Marks
- b. You are in charge of the Emergency Ward of your hospital. How would you use management functions to manage your ward. - 14 Marks

QUESTION THREE

- a. State and briefly explain **four (4)** purpose of a budget. - 4 marks
- b. The matron of Holy family hospital Berekum, maintains a good bookkeeping hence has just been given a cash float of **GHS100** by the accountant of the hospital to help cater for any petty expenses or disbursement at the ward. During the month, the matron purchase tea for **GHS 8**, pay travel expenses of **GHS 35**, purchase sundry stationery worth **GHS18** and purchase gloves for **GHS48**.
 - i) How much reimbursement will be required at the end of the month? - 2 marks
 - ii) By how much balance will she have on hand at the end of the month? - 2 marks
 - iii) Estimate the total receipts at the close of the transaction. - 2 marks
- c.
 - i) Define **bookkeeping** and briefly explain any **three (3)** elements of financial management. - 4 marks
 - ii) You want to have GHS 20 million for retirement in 35 years. You invested in a mutual fund paying an average of 18.75% interest each year compounded weekly. How much will you deposit into your mutual fund? - 3 marks
 - iii) State and briefly explain the **three (3)** key decision usually made by financial managers of organization. - 3marks

QUESTION FOUR

- a. Describe the process of receiving materials into store system. - 2 marks
- b. What is coding? Give one (1) benefit of coding. - 2 marks
- c. State Four (4) things/conditions that General Stores should be protected from - 2 marks
- d. List Four (4) equipment used in stores - 2 marks
- e. State the Four (4) kinds of inventory received by stores - 2 marks
- f. What is Store-Keeping? - 2 marks
 - i. State the types of stores? - 1 mark
 - ii. Briefly explain the types of stores - 2 marks
 - iii. Outline four functions performed by the stores department - 2 marks
- e. Briefly explain the four sections in the process of storekeeping - 2 marks
 - i. Name any two (2) store records you can find in the stores - 1 mark

INDEX NUMBER.....

HFNMTC – BEREKUM

END OF SEMESTER EXAMINATION – JULY 2020

PBM 2: MANAGEMENT AND ADMINISTRATION IN MIDWIFERY

TIME ALLOWED: 1HR.

OBJECTIVES

INSTRUCTIONS

- Answer all questions
- Each question must be answered in a separate answer booklet
- Each question carries 20 marks.
- Read the questions carefully and provide only the relevant answers
- Note that any number of points provide beyond the NUMBER SPECIFIED for each question will attract any mark

Question One

Madam Mary Dickson has been appointed as the New Human Resource Manager of Kokofu Hospital. She has the intention of improving organizational effectiveness through people.

- a. Mention **FIVE (5)** functions of a Human Resource Manager. - 5 marks
- b. Mention **FIVE (5)** qualities of an effective leader - 5 marks
- c. Mention **FIVE (5)** leadership styles apart from the style applied by Mrs. Dickson - 5marks
- d. Give Five (5) purposes of report writing - 5 marks

FINANCE

Question Two (a)

- a. State and briefly explain four (4) purpose of a budget. - 4 marks
- b. The matron of Holy family hospital Berekum, maintains a good bookkeeping hence has just been given a cash float of **GHS100** by the accountant of the hospital to help cater for any petty expenses or disbursement at the ward. During the month, the matron purchase tea for **GHS 8**, pay travel expenses of **GHS 35**, purchase sundry stationery worth **GHS18** and purchase gloves for **GHS48**.
 - i) How much reimbursement will be required at the end of the month? - 2 marks
 - ii) By how much balance will she have on hand at the end of the month? - 2 marks
- c. Estimate the total receipts at the close of the transaction. - 2 marks

STORES

Question Two (b)

- i. Describe the process of receiving materials into store system. - 2 marks
- ii. Explain the three (3) basic functions of the store keeper. - 3marks
- iii. Compare and contrast the difference between the two types of stores. - 3marks
- iv. What is coding? Give one (1) benefit of coding. - 2marks

HFNMTC – BEREKUM
END OF SEMESTER EXAMINATION – JULY 2020
PNNM2 MANAGEMENT AND ADMINISTRATION IN MIDWIFERY
TIME ALLOWED: 1 HR.
ESSAY

Instructions:

- Answer all questions
- Each question carries 20 marks
- Read the question carefully and provide only relevant answers
- Note that any number of points provided beyond the **NUMBER SPECIFIED** will not attract any mark

Question

- a. As a CEO of Korle Bu Teaching Hospital, a workshop was organized by a group of facilitators on the Topic **'Time Value of Money'** for the purpose of your role in the hospital and as part of your job to improve the financial health of your facility, and by way of sharing with your staffs what you have learned, Required;
- i) Give FOUR (4) golden rules in financing - 2 marks
- ii) State any THREE (3) Objectives of financial management - 3 marks
- b. You want to have GHS 20 million for retirement in 35 years. You invested in a mutual fund paying an average of 18.75% interest each year compounded weekly. How much will you deposit into your mutual fund? - 2 marks
- c. State and briefly explain the three (3) key decision usually made by financial managers of organization. 3marks

INDEX NUMBER.....
HFNMTC – BEREKUM/ST. MARY'S CAMPUS - DROBO
END OF SEMESTER EXAMINATION - MAY 2018
RGN 19 RGN 222 MANAGEMENT AND ADMINISTRATION IN NURSING
TIME ALLOWED:2 HRS
ESSAY

Instructions:

- Answer all questions.
- Each question must be answered in a separate booklet
- Each question carries 20marks
- Read the question carefully and provide only relevant answers
- Note that any number of points provided beyond the NUMBER SPECIFIED for each question will not attract any mark.

Management

Question One

- a. Give any three (3) advantages and three (3) disadvantages of a pyramidal organizational structure. - 6 marks
- b. You are in charge of the Emergency Ward of your hospital. How would you use management functions to manage your ward. - 14 Marks

Question Two

- a. State four (4) advantages and four disadvantages of an Autocratic Leadership Style - 8 marks
- b. Mention five (5) benefits of managing your time effectively. - 5 marks
- c. State three(3) principles of quality assurance - 3 marks
- d. List any four (4) stages of team building - 4 marks

Finance

Question Three

- a. State and explain the three (3) key decision usually made by financial managers of organizations.- 6 marks
- b. List and briefly explain five (5) characteristics of Accounting information - 10 marks
- c. State and briefly explain four (4) purpose of a budget - 4 marks

Question Four

Stores.

- a. Describe the process of receiving materials into store system - 2 marks
- b. Explain the three (3) basic functions of the store keeper. - 3marks
- c. List three (3) examples of the following category of items held in stores:
 - i Raw materials
 - ii Finished goods- 3marks
- d. Explain the functions of accounting section and issuing section of stores department. - 4marks
- e. What is a decentralised store? - 1mark
- f. Give two (2) merits and demerits of decentralized stores. - 2marks
- g. Compare the difference between the two types of stores. - 3marks
- h. Simply explain Coding with a benefit - 2marks

INDEX NUMBER.....

HFNMTC-BEREKUM/ ST. MARY'S CAMPUS - DROBO

END OF SEMESTER EXAMINATION - MAY 2017

RGN 18 & RM 13 RGN 212 / RMD 321 MANAGEMENT IN NURSING & MIDWIFERY

TIME ALLOWED:- 2 HOURS

ESSAY

INSTRUCTIONS:

- Answer all questions.
- Each question must be answered in a separate answer booklet
- Each question carries 20 marks
- Read the question carefully and provide only relevant answers

Note that any number of points provided beyond the NUMBER SPECIFIED for each question will not attract any marks

Question One

- a. Briefly explain the following as used in division and coordination of Labour in an organization:
- i. Chain of Command - 2 Marks
 - ii. Span of Control - 2 Marks
 - iii. Centralization - 2 Marks
 - iv. Specialization - 2 Marks
 - v. Departmentalization - 2 Marks
- b. Failing to manage your time effectively can have some very undesirable consequences. State four of these undesirable consequences. - 4 marks
- c. Give any three advantages and three disadvantages of a pyramidal organizational structure. - 6 marks

Question Two

You are in charge of the Maternity Ward or Emergency Ward of your hospital. How would you use management functions to manage your ward? - 20 marks

Question Three

are Allocated Ledger

Date	Voucher No	Particulars	Received	Issued	Balance in Stock	Unit Price	Amt.

Store Receipt Voucher No. 0001

Date	Voucher No	Received	Qty.	Description Of Good	Price	Amount	Ledger Number/ Folio	Remarks
17/05/17	000005	Gerard Pharma	2000	Amoxycillin	0.50	1,000	0 1 0	Good

Date: 17/05/17

Store Keeper

NMTC – BEREKUM/ ST. MARY'S CAMPUS, DROBO
END OF SEMESTER EXAMINATION- MAY 2016
RGN 17 & RM 12 - MANAGEMENT AND ADMINISTRATION IN NURSING / MIDWIFERY
TIME ALLOWED: 2Hrs.

ESSAY

INSTRUCTIONS:

- Answer all questions.
- Each question must be answered in a separate answer booklet
- Each question carries 20 marks
- Read the question carefully and provide only relevant answers

Note that any number of points provided beyond the NUMBER SPECIFIED for each question will not attract any marks

Question One

- a. Mention any three (3) advantages of democratic leadership. - 3 marks
- b. Outline any five (5) differences between a leader and a manager - 5 marks
- Discuss communication under the following headings:
- c. Definition - 2 marks
- d. Communication skills - 5 marks
- e. Barriers to communication - 5 marks

Question Two

- a. Mention five (5) Quality Assurance Principles - 5marks
- b. The newly appointed medical superintendent of a government hospital has approached you as a student nurse or midwife who has knowledge in organizational structure to give him five reasons why it is necessary to have an organizational structure in the hospital. - 5marks
- c. Explain five main elements of planning. - 5 marks
- d. Failing to manage your time effectively can have some very undesirable consequences. State five of these undesirable consequences. - 5 marks

Question Three

- a. Raw materials
- i. Finished goods - 3marks
- ii. Describe the process of receiving materials into store system. - 2marks
- iii. Explain the three (3) basic functions of the store keeper. - 3marks
- iv. List three (3) examples of the following category of items held in stores:
- b. Explain the functions of accounting section and issuing section of stores department. . - 4marks
- i. What is a decentralised store? Give two (2) merits and demerits of decentralized stores - 3marks
- ii. Compare and contrast the difference between the two types of stores. - 3marks
- iii. What is coding? Give one (1) benefit of coding. - 2marks

Question Four.

On January 4, 2016, a petty cashier was given a cash float of GHC1,000.00 for the month ended 31st January, 2016. Reimbursement was made as and when necessary. Expenditures incurred for the month were as follows:

		GHC
January 4	Travelling expenses	108.00
January 5	Postage stamps	84.00
January 5	Napkins	85.00
January 7	Taxi fare	88.00
January 8	Duplicating sheets	100.00
January 8	Petrol	85.00
January 11	Envelops	164.00
January 13	Postage stamps	36.00
January 14	Soap for cleaning	59.00
January 15	Taxi fare	241.00
January 18	Napkins	109.00
January 18	Petrol	185.00
January 20	Correction fluid	55.00
January 22	Envelops	22.00
January 25	Postage stamps	30.00
January 29	Detergent	87.00

You are required to write up the petty cash book for the month of January, 2016.

END OF SEMESTER EXAMINATION APRIL 2013
RGN 14/RM – 9 HRGN 044/ HMDW 057 MANAGEMENT AND NURSING ADMINISTRATION
TIME ALLOWED: 2Hrs.
ESSAY

Instructions:

- Answer all questions.
- Each question must be answered in a separate answer booklet
- Each question carries 20 marks.
- Read the question carefully and provide only relevant answers.
- Note that any number of points provided beyond the NUMBER SPECIFIED for each question will not attract any marks.

Question One

Team work plays a significant role in the achievement of organizational goals.

- a. i. Explain clearly three (3) factors that promote effective team work Any 3 points = 6 marks
- ii. Describe to your junior colleague two (2) factors that impede effective team work Any 2 points = 4 marks
- b. List five (5) benefits of Quality Assurance to health care managers 5 marks
- c. i. List four (4) functions of management
- ii. Define the following terms in management
- a. Effectiveness
- b. Efficiency

Total mark = 5

Question Two

- a. You are the ward in – charge of Ward B. How will you manage your ward space to achieve the organizational goal? 10marks
- b. Enumerate seven (7) effects of poor quality health care 3 marks
- c. In recent times quality health care is the concern of every nation. Describe Quality Health Care to your junior colleague using the dimensions of quality 7 marks

Question Three

Finance

- a. As an Accountant of Nana Boakye Company LTD, state five importance of keeping financial Records
- b. From the following Balances as at 31st December 2012, prepare a Balance Sheet for Thomas Williams Trading Enterprise.

Item	GH¢
Fixtures and Fittings	500.00
Debtors	680.00
Creditors	910.00
Stock	300.00
Bank	1,510.00
Cash	20.00
Capital	2,100.00

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NMTC – BEREKUM
 END OF SEMESTER EXAMINATION JUNE 2014
DIPLOMA 15, HRGN 044/HMDW 057 MANAGEMENT AND ADMINISTRATION IN NURSING
 TIME ALLOWED: 1 1/2 Hrs.

ESSAY

Instructions:

- Answer all questions.
- Each question must be answered in a separate answer booklet
- Each question carries 20 marks.
- Read the question carefully and provide only relevant answers.

Note that any number of points provided beyond the NUMBER SPECIFIED for each question will not attract any marks.

Question One

A Quality health care has been an important issue in Ghana in recent times, using the attributes that contribute to health care quality.

- a. Describe how you would ensure quality health care to your client as a ward manager - 8 marks
- b. Communications plays a significant role in effectiveness team building
- i. Draw the communication circle - 2marks
- ii. Explain in details the components of the communication circle - 10 marks

Question Two

- i. The D15 Class invested GHC100,000 at 10 percent interest for ten years with the interest compounded annually. What is the value of the investment at the end of the tenth year and how much interest will the Class earn at the end of the tenth year? - 15marks
- ii. State and explain the two main objectives of financial management and three functions of financial manager. - 5marks

Question Three

Store allocated ledger

Date	Voucher No.	Particulars	Received	Issued	Bal in stock	Unit price	Amount
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Store

Receipt

Voucher

No. 0001

Date	Voucher No.	Received from	Quantity	Description of goods	Price	Amount	Ledged No	Remarks
2/06/14	005	Gerard Pharma	2000	Amoxicillin capsules 250mg	0.50	1,000	010	G Y

Date 2/06/14

Requisition book

- Emergency ward requisition No. 100 date: 02/06/14
- Female ward requisition No. 200 date: 03/06/14
- Males ward requisition No. 300 date: 04/06/14

The above wards requested for 500 amyxcellin capsules 250g each on different dates

- a. Copy and complete the store allocated ledger - 5 marks
- b. Issue to the request of the Emergency Ward - 5 marks
- c. Grant the requisition of the Female Ward - 5 marks
- d. Attend to the request of the Male Ward lessen/ lesser by 100 capsules - 5 marks

NMTC – BEREKUM/ ST. MARY'S CAMPUS, DROBO
END OF SEMESTER EXAMINATION- MAY 2016
RGN 17 & RM 12 - MANAGEMENT AND ADMINISTRATION IN NURSING / MIDWIFERY
TIME ALLOWED: 2Hrs.

ESSAY

INSTRUCTIONS:

- Answer all questions.
- Each question must be answered in a separate answer booklet
- Each question carries 20 marks
- Read the question carefully and provide only relevant answers

Note that any number of points provided beyond the NUMBER SPECIFIED for each question will not attract any marks

Question One

- a. Mention any three (3) advantages of democratic leadership. - 3 marks
- b. Outline any five (5) differences between a leader and a manager - 5 marks
- Discuss communication under the following headings:
- c. Definition - 2 marks
- Communication skills - 5 marks
- Barriers to communication - 5 marks

Question Two

- a. Mention five (5) Quality Assurance Principles - 5marks
- b. The newly appointed medical superintendent of a government hospital has approached you as a student nurse or midwife who has knowledge in organizational structure to give him five reasons why it is necessary to have an organizational structure in the hospital. - 5marks
- c. Explain five main elements of planning. - 5 marks
- d. Failing to manage your time effectively can have some very undesirable consequences. State five of these undesirable consequences. - 5 marks

Question Three

- a. Raw materials
- i. Finished goods - 3marks
- ii. Describe the process of receiving materials into store system. - 2marks
- iii. Explain the three (3) basic functions of the store keeper. - 3marks
- iv. List three (3) examples of the following category of items held in stores:
- b. Explain the functions of accounting section and issuing-section of stores department. - 4marks
- i. What is a decentralised store? Give two (2) merits and demerits of decentralized stores - 3marks
- ii. Compare and contrast the difference between the two types of stores. - 3marks
- iii. What is coding? Give one (1) benefit of coding. - 2marks

INDEX NUMBER.....

HOLY FNMTC-BEREKUM
END OF SEMESTER EXAMINATION- MAY 2019
RM 14: MANAGEMENT AND ADMINISTRATION IN MIDWIFERY: RMD 321
TIME ALLOWED: 2HOURS
ESSAY

INSTRUCTIONS:

- Answer all questions
- Each question must be answered in a separate booklet
- Each question carries 20marks
- Read the question carefully and provide only relevant answers
- Note that any number of points provided beyond the NUMBER SPECIFIED for each question will not attract any mark.

QUESTION ONE

- a. Explain briefly any **five (5)** dimensions of quality. - 10 Marks
- b. List the **five (5)** main Quality Assurance Principles - 5 Marks
- c. Mention any **five (5)** differences between a leader and a manager - 5 Marks

QUESTION TWO

- a. Mention any **three (3)** advantages and **three (3)** disadvantages of a pyramidal organisational structure. - 6 Marks
- b. You are in charge of the Emergency Ward of your hospital. How would you use management functions to manage your ward. - 14 Marks

QUESTION THREE

- a. State and briefly explain **four (4)** purpose of a budget. - 4 marks
- b. The matron of Holy family hospital Berekum, maintains a good bookkeeping hence has just been given a cash float of **GHS100** by the accountant of the hospital to help cater for any petty expenses or disbursement at the ward. During the month, the matron purchase tea for **GHS 8**, pay travel expenses of **GHS 35**, purchase sundry stationery worth **GHS18** and purchase gloves for **GHS48**.
 - i) How much reimbursement will be required at the end of the month? - 2 marks
 - ii) By how much balance will she have on hand at the end of the month? - 2 marks
 - iii) Estimate the total receipts at the close of the transaction. - 2 marks
- c.
 - i) Define **bookkeeping** and briefly explain any **three (3)** elements of financial management. - 4 marks
 - ii) You want to have GHS 20 million for retirement in 35 years. You invested in a mutual fund paying an average of 18.75% interest each year compounded weekly. How much will you deposit into your mutual fund? - 3 marks
 - iii) State and briefly explain the **three (3)** key decision usually made by financial managers of organization. - 3marks

INDEX NUMBER.....
HFNMTC – BEREKUM
END OF SEMESTER EXAMINATION – JULY 2020
PBM 2: MANAGEMENT AND ADMINISTRATION IN MIDWIFERY
TIME ALLOWED: 1HR.
OBJECTIVES

INSTRUCTIONS

- Answer all questions
- Each question must be answered in a separate answer booklet
- Each question carries 20 marks.
- Read the questions carefully and provide only the relevant answers
- Note that any number of points provided beyond the NUMBER SPECIFIED for each question will attract any mark

Question One

Madam Mary Dickson has been appointed as the New Human Resource Manager of Kokofu Hospital. She has the intention of improving organizational effectiveness through people.

- a. Mention FIVE (5) functions of a Human Resource Manager. - 5 marks
- b. Mention FIVE (5) qualities of an effective leader - 5 marks
- c. Mention FIVE (5) leadership styles apart from the style applied by Mrs. Dickson - 5marks
- d. Give Five (5) purposes of report writing - 5 marks

FINANCE

Question Two (a)

- a. State and briefly explain four (4) purpose of a budget. - 4 marks
- b. The matron of Holy family hospital Berekum, maintains a good bookkeeping hence has just been given a cash float of GHS100 by the accountant of the hospital to help cater for any petty expenses or disbursement at the ward. During the month, the matron purchase tea for GHS 8, pay travel expenses of GHS 35, purchase sundry stationery worth GHS18 and purchase gloves for GHS48.
 - i) How much reimbursement will be required at the end of the month? - 2 marks
 - ii) By how much balance will she have on hand at the end of the month? - 2 marks
- c. Estimate the total receipts at the close of the transaction. - 2 marks

STORES

Question Two (b)

- i. Describe the process of receiving materials into store system. - 2 marks
- ii. Explain the three (3) basic functions of the store keeper. - 3marks
- iii. Compare and contrast the difference between the two types of stores. - 3marks
- iv. What is coding? Give one (1) benefit of coding. - 2marks

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HOLY FNMTC-BEREKUM
END OF SEMESTER EXAMINATION- MAY 2019
RM 14: MANAGEMENT AND ADMINISTRATION IN MIDWIFERY: RMD 321
TIME ALLOWED: 2HOURS

ESSAY

INSTRUCTIONS:

- Answer all questions
- Each question must be answered in a separate booklet
- Each question carries 20marks
- Read the question carefully and provide only relevant answers
- Note that any number of points provided beyond the NUMBER SPECIFIED for each question will not attract any mark.

QUESTION ONE

Mrs B.C. is a Senior Nurse Manager at St. Pauls's Hospital in the Western Region. She has 12 nurses in her team and she is the team leader in her Department and a Management Member of the Hospital. The relationship between Mrs. B.C. and the nurses is cordial and team members are often highly engaged in projects and decision - making process leading to high productivity and job satisfaction.

- a. What leadership style is Mrs. B. C. applying in her work situation? - 2 marks
- b. Mention 5 other leadership styles apart from the style applied by Mrs. B.C. - 5 marks
- c. Mention 3 disadvantages of the leadership style applied by Mrs. B.C. - 5 marks
- d. Briefly explain the differences between Management and Administration - 8 marks

QUESTION TWO

As a Midwife, you recently took over a new role as the Manager of Maternity Ward. With a high level of commitment and motivation though new in the hospital, you ensure that processes and procedures and other resources are used in an efficient and effective manner. The ward has a bed capacity of 24 with 7 newly posted midwives.

Describe Ward Management under the following:

- a. Management of newly posted midwives - 5 marks
- b. Management of client care - 5 marks
- c. Management of the environment - 5 marks
- d. Management of supplies and equipment - 5 marks

QUESTION THREE

Store Allocated Ledger

Date	Voucher No	Particulars	Received	Issued	Balance in Stock	Unit Price	Amt.

Store Receipt Voucher No. 0010

Date	Voucher No	Received From	Qty.	Description Of Good	Price	Amount	Ledger Number/ Folio	Remarks
22/05/19	00015	RM 14 Pharma	5000	Amoxycillin 250mg	0.75	3750.00	15D	Good

Date: 24/05/19

Store Keeper *[Signature]*

Requisition Book

Emergency Ward Requisition No. 518 date 27/05/19

Females Ward Requisition No. 243 date 27/05/19

Males Ward Requisition No. 630 date 27/05/19

The above Wards requested for 1500 Amoxycillin Capsules of 250mg each on this dates.

Task

1. Copy and complete the store allocated ledger. - 5 marks
2. Issue to the request of the Emergency Ward. - 5marks
3. Grant the request of the Female Ward. - 5marks
4. Attend to the request of the Male Ward lessen/ lesser by 100 capsules - 5marks

QUESTION FOUR

Heal the world enterprise maintains a petty cash book for the month of May 2019 in relation to the following petty transaction: On 1st May, 2019 a cash float GHS 1,600.00 was given and the following payments were effected:

	GHS
May 2: Postage stamps purchased	100
May 3: Wages for errand boy	200
May 5: Cost of registered letters	240
May 6: Stationery	200
May 7: Stamps pad	160
May 10: Cleaning	100
May 12: Wages	200
May 14: Bought Arc files	120
May 18: Paid for omo	70
May 19: Casual labour	200
May 20: Carbon papers	80
May 25: Stamp pad ink	40
May 27: Washing powder	80
May 30: fees for post office box	160

Required: Prepare a petty cash book

- 20 marks